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Reproductive Behaviour in *Agapornis roseicollis*

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Abstract

Agapornis roseicollis commonly known worldwide as rosy-faced or peach-faced African lovebird has got much recognition as a pet in recent years. When the African continent was explored, the western world also made acquaintance with lovebirds. The first variety to be scientifically described in 1788 was *Agapornis pullarius* and the last was a subspecies of *Agapornis roseicollis*, *Agapornis roseicollis catumbella*, which was scientifically registered as late as 1955. In the ongoing research, a study was conducted on a colony of lovebirds to understand the reproductive behaviour during the breeding season under captivity. All the birds under study were of an average age of 12-14 months. All the essential external factors like photoperiod, food availability, temperature, humidity etc. which could affect the reproductive behaviour were maintained. The birds were closely monitored, and remarkable behavioural changes were observed with respect to feeding, nesting, territorial behaviour and mating rituals. This paper is important as good knowledge of reproductive behaviour may be of paramount significance to understanding the factors affecting reproductive success and developing a conservation management plan if the species gets threatened or endangered in the near future.

Keywords: African lovebirds; Avian Ethology; Reproductive behaviour; Mate selection; Mating behaviour; Parrots

Introduction

The genus *Agapornis* is from the Greek words agapein (to caress) and ornis (bird). Lovebirds are given this name because they mate for life, that is they strictly follow monogamy. Within the genus *Agapornis*, there are nine species and their subspecies, which adds up to a total of fifteen varieties. The genus *Agapornis* includes the following species and their sub species which are summarised in Table 1.

Our behavioural study was performed on *Agapornis roseicollis* or commonly called Peach-faced or rosy-cheeked lovebirds. These birds are 15 cm long and weigh around 50g on average. Females are larger in size in comparison to males. The Rosy-faced lovebird exhibits variation in colour with age. Males usually have bright plumage in comparison to females which are slightly pale or dull. The variation in colour may be associated with Evolutionary significance for Mate selection. They have bright red forehead which extends down to the upper breast and laterally to chins and throats. The rest of the body is green with a bright bluish rump. The young develop bright plumage after their 1st moulting at an average age of 4 months.

Agapornis roseicollis are often found living in flocks of more than 5 birds and are very communal species communicating with each other in various manners. They are diurnal in nature, leaving their nests early in the morning and returning back to their respective nests by evening.

Study area and set up

Ten successfully bonded, aged 12-14 months *Agapornis roseicollis* (Rosy-faced lovebirds) pairs were left in a colony of dimension (15ft x 10ft x 10ft) in the month of January 2021 and were monitored till late May 2021. The optimum conditions were provided for successful uninterrupted breeding so as to capture stereotypical reproductive behavioural changes. The birds were fed on a variety of millets, green veggies, fruits etc. Nest boxes of dimension (10" x 8" x 8") were introduced on 15th Jan 21. The nesting material included dried twigs, fresh coconut and palm leaves.

Peach-faced lovebirds are among the most popular caged bird from the genus *Agapornis* and are found in lots of different mutations. They feed on a variety of seeds commonly found in Acacia and Albizia. (Ndithia and Perrin, 2006a) These little birds living in hot arid regions are known to drink water several times a day.

Table 1. Species and subspecies under Genus *Agapornis*.

S.no	SPECIES
1.	<i>Agapornis canus canus</i> (Gmelin, 1788)
2.	<i>Agapornis canus ablectaneus</i> (Bangs, 1918)
3.	<i>Agapornis taranta taranta</i> (Stanley, 1814)
4.	<i>Agapornis pullarius pullarius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)
5.	<i>Agapornis pullarius ugandae</i> (Neumann, 1908)
6.	<i>Agapornis swindernianus swindernianus</i> (kuhl, 1820)
7.	<i>Agapornis swindernianus zenkeri</i> (Reichenow, 1895)
8.	<i>Agapornis swindernianus emini</i> (Neumann, 1908)
9.	<i>Agapornis roseicollis roseicollis</i> (Vieillot, 1818)
10.	<i>Agapornis roseicollis catumbella</i> (Hall, 1952)
11.	<i>Agapornis personatus</i> (Reichenow, 1887)
12.	<i>Agapornis fischeri</i> (Reichenow, 1887)
13.	<i>Agapornis nigrigenis</i> (Sclater, 1906)
14.	<i>Agapornis lilianae</i> (Shelley, 1894)

The male exhibits an interesting behaviour known as sidling while approaching a potential mate. In Sidling the male moves in a sideways manner towards the female. If the female is not interested or receptive, she will chase him away, meanwhile, the male will approach her from the other side. This is known as Switch sidling. If the female is sexually receptive, she will exhibit a fluffed posture with wings widespread and tail up. The formation of bonds may start as soon as at an age of 2-3 months. In rosy-faced lovebird Females are dominant. Siblings may form pairs which are very common. They are also found looking for their own nests after pair formation. Males were often seen feeding females during courtship. Scratching each other at the forehead or beak is also common during courtship. Rosy-faced lovebirds can breed for a whole year in captivity as long as external factors are maintained. They are Seasonal breeders in the wild (Rowan, 1983).

The Maturation of the ovary and oviduct are synchronized with nest-building behaviour and the development of brood patches in females. Both the parents take active participation in feeding the chicks. A change in abiotic factors such as Rain, photoperiod, temperature etc. leads to increased activity of the pituitary which stimulates the onset of the breeding season. The pituitary secretes gonadotrophins which are responsible for the growth of gonads in both males and females. After the maturation of gonads, they release hormones which in association with exogenous factors stimulate various reproductive behaviour such as courtship, territorial behaviour, mate competition etc. (Eisner, 2004). Estrogen hormone is responsible for nesting behaviour in females, which is again in accordance with a minimum age (Orcutt, 1997).

In males, high levels of testosterone and gonadotrophins are associated with aggressiveness, courtship displays, Mate competitions, parental care etc. Males do not participate in the incubation process. An increased level of Prolactin and decreased level of steroid hormones is responsible for the initiation of incubation in females (Ketterson et al., 2006). Rosy-faced lovebirds seem to synchronize the egg-laying time and incubation with abiotic factors such as rainfall, photoperiod, and abundance of food. They feed on seeds hence a second clutch will be attempted or not, totally depending upon external environmental factors such as food availability (Ndithia et al., 2007). In terms of nest-site selection, most pairs prefer top corner nests facing west (Alonso and Muñoz-Pulido, 1991). The *Agapornis roseicollis* exhibits a characteristic nest-building behaviour in which females initially shred long leaves into small pieces and then using their beaks tuck them into their rump and fly to the nesting site (Eberhard, 1998).

The female lays a single egg on alternate days. During this period male feeds, the partner mostly while she spends the majority of her time in the nest. In Rosy-faced lovebirds, the average incubation period is 23 days. Regurgitation is the mode of feeding the chicks by parents. Males fly to feeding grounds, consume seeds and get back to the nest to regurgitate the food into the female's mouth. The female regurgitates the food into the young's mouth during the initial period of hatching, which was later done by both the parents until the babies are fully weaned.

The onset of the second clutch engages females into nesting behaviour while chicks leave the nest at an average of 42 days. After which they are often seen being close to male parent for food. Rosy-faced lovebirds in captivity build their own respective nests. They build deep cup-like nests using various nesting materials like palm leaves and grass twigs. (De Grahl, 1984; Rowan, 1983; Vriends, 1978).

Observations

The colony was closely monitored to get a better understanding of changes that occur during the reproductive phases of *Agapornis roseicollis*.

Nest selection and nest-building behaviour

On the introduction of nest boxes, the females were found inspecting the nest boxes with curious nature and a keen interest in moving from one box to another. Males were seen guarding the nest boxes while sitting on top of the nest or near the entrance (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Rosy-faced loved selecting their nest boxes

Fig. 2. After selection of nest box and nest box guarding

The selection of nest boxes took an average of 2 days. Nest boxes at the top corner were of more interest to the birds. Once the respective nest boxes were selected by the pairs, they were often seen spending most of the time in nest boxes or sitting above the nest boxes (Fig. 2). The nesting material was provided to the birds one day after the selection of boxes. The majority of interest in nest building was performed by the females however sometimes male was also seen doing the same. An interesting characteristic of nest-building behaviour is seen in *Agapornis roseicollis* species. Female birds were seen shredding the leaves and tucking 4-5 cut pieces of leaves into her rump and then making a flight directly to the nest box top or entrance.

Mating behaviour and courtship

On completion of the nest-building process, the pair spends most of their time preening and feeding each other. Scratching the partner during courtship is observed as a sign of bonding and affection. Both male and female scratch each other forehead and beak (Fig.3.). Males were often observed feeding their partner (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Female (Middle) in demand of scratching from male (left)

Fig. 4. Male (left) about to feed female.

When a male is trying to approach a female, he creeps toward her in a sideways fashion known as sidling. If she appears aggressive, he tries to approach her from the other side in a process known as switch sidling; however, if she seems receptive, he continues sidling toward her. If the female is receptive, it will sit down with its tail up and wings widespread (Fig. 5) then the male will mount the back of the female often holding the flight feathers of the female to get a good grip for copulation. The mating occurs for a few seconds and is repeated numerous times a day. If the female is not receptive it will try to catch the male legs or fly away.

Territorial or aggressive behaviour

Once the female is copulated by the male, the egg development process begins with remarkable behavioural changes. The female will spend most of her time sitting inside the box and the male will guard

it. The hormonal changes during the reproductive phase induce aggression and territorial behaviour. Females or males were observed scaring away other birds nearby to the nest box. Females were also seen occupying more than one nest box and avoiding other pairs to select one. Aggression towards males is not uncommon.

Fig. 5. Receptive female (Middle) with wings widespread and tail up.

Infanticides by the female parent

Although infanticides in animals at majority of time are performed by male parent so as to increase their fitness (reproductive fitness) however, in *Agapornis roseicollis* female were often seen not feeding the last hatched chicks and resulting in death. Siblicide is also observed where elder siblings do not allow the last hatched chicks to get fed by the parent.

Egg laying and incubation

After approximately 7 days of successful fertilization, the female lays the first egg (Fig. 6). A clutch usually consists of 4-6 eggs and is laid on alternate days (Fig. 7). Females usually take part in the active incubation process once the second egg is laid. Males do not incubate the eggs in *roseicollis* species however they are found accompanying the females by sitting next to them in nest boxes. Incubation lasts for around 23 days. Females lose a lot of their body weight during this process.

Fig. 6. Female after laying 1st egg in the nest box.

Fig. 7. Female with 4 eggs, incubation starts after the second egg is laid.

Hatching and rearing of chicks

The chicks usually hatch out of eggs on 21st day after the onset of incubation. A pinhole is created by the fully developed chick which helps in breaking the shell and coming out of the egg (Fig. 8). In certain conditions, the egg shell is deposited with extra calcium thus making it difficult for the chick to break it and thus resulting in a dead in shell condition. Vitamin D₃ seems to be so crucial for the same.

Fig. 8. Newly hatched rosy-faced lovebird chick and 3 fertile eggs

Fig. 9. Female rosy-faced lovebird with 2 chicks recently fed

The chicks are fed every 2 hours on the 1st day of hatching, these hours of feeding are reduced as the chick grows (Fig. 9). Both parents take active participation in the rearing of chicks. They are fed with a rich source of proteins and carbohydrates for better growth and development. The chicks are ready to leave the nest after almost 40 days. Chicks after leaving the nest were observed sitting on the floor, on perches, or top of the nest box. Male Parent was often found protecting the chicks from other adult birds in the colony as they may injure the chicks due to territorial aggression.

Second clutch preparation

Females were observed mating for the second clutch even before the chicks are fully weaned. Some females lay their eggs when the chicks of the last clutch are still in boxes. This seems to provide a disadvantage as chicks are found destroying or breaking the eggs while they are getting fed. The male parent takes care of the chicks while the female is busy preparing the nest or getting prepared for an egg-laying process (Fig. 10 & Fig. 11).

Fig. 10. Male rosy-faced lovebird (left) with its chick.

Fig. 11. Male rosy-faced lovebird (left) feeding its chick.

Results

Agapornis roseicollis, commonly known as peach-faced or rosy-faced lovebirds are social colonial birds. The breeding biology including, feeding behaviour, intraspecific competition, mate selection, nesting behaviour, mating behaviour etc. was closely observed and analysis is represented in Table 2.

Table 2. Behavioural observations

S.no	BEHAVIOUR	EXHIBITED BY MALE	EXHIBITED BY FEMALE
1.	Feeding chicks	YES	YES
2.	Incubation	NO	YES
3.	Nesting	NO	YES
4.	Territorial protection	YES	YES
5.	Courtship	YES	NO
6.	Mate selection	NO	YES
7.	Parental care	YES	YES
8.	Intraspecific competition for nest	NO	YES
9.	Infanticide	NO	YES
10.	Siblicide	YES	NO

Discussion

The study was undertaken at Khalsa College Amritsar, Punjab. In the ongoing study, we tried to get a depth insight into behavioural changes which occurs during the reproductive phase of rosy-faced love birds. The experimental setup was monitored closely to capture the stereotype behaviour. The birds were left in the colony for five months (1st January 2021 to 1st June 2021). After the introduction of nest boxes, females were seen inspecting the nest boxes followed by the male's approval for it. An elevated level of Estrogen hormone seems to be essential for stimulation of nesting behaviour, mate selection etc. in females which was also seen in a study previously done by Orcutt (1997).

Feeding chicks or parental care is exhibited by both parents. In males, high levels of testosterone and gonadotrophins are associated with aggressiveness, courtship displays, Mate competitions, parental care etc. Males do not participate in the incubation process. An increased level of Prolactin and decreased level of steroid hormones is responsible for the initiation of incubation in females (Ketterson et al., 2006). The boxes at the top corner were of most interest to birds same as observed by (Alonso and Muñoz-Pulido, 1991). A unique characteristic of rosy-faced lovebirds was tucking the nesting material into their rump while the nest construction process was also observed in a study conducted by Eberhard (1998). Parents were observed with aggression and territorial behaviour which was supposed to be associated with high levels of gonadotrophins as concluded by experimentation done by Eisner (2004).

Parental care was female-biased however male was seen raising the chicks when the female prepares for her second clutch. Parental care, feeding, and competition for nesting sites were associated with high levels of prolactin and testosterone. An increased level of prolactin in females results in such female-biased parental care during the initial period of rearing which was evidenced by Ketterson et al. (2006). The female tends to start preparing for its second clutch which was closely associated with photoperiod, availability of food, and rainfall (Ndithia et al., 2007). The same observations were also reported in our study since there was no shortage of food under captivity and great concern was given to the photoperiod factor by us.

Conclusion

The present study enabled us to get an overall idea of the breeding biology of the rosy-faced lovebird. Significant knowledge of this would be a great asset in the field of ornithology and veterinary sciences. Consequently, it would be of paramount importance if the species in the near future come to endangered or vulnerable status. This would also assist in understanding the behaviour associated with reproductive systems, the mechanism of hormonal regulation, and the role of various vitamins like Vitamin D₃, in poultry and egg production.

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Author Contributions

JKR and LS conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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The author declares no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

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